

Influence of Social Activities on Social Adjustment of Students with Deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria

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Abstract:- The study investigated the influence of social activities on social adjustment of students with deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria. The purpose of the study is to ascertain the influence of social activities on social adjustment of students with deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Four null hypotheses were postulated to guide the research. The variables include participation in game (sport), creative drama activity, gender and play competition. To collect data effectively, 12 item questionnaire was administered on 100 respondents sampled for study. The data collected were analysed using z-test statistic to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that gender has no influence on social adjustment of students with deafness rather there are substantial influence of participation in games (sport), creative drama activity and play competition therefore, based on these findings some recommendations, suggestions that are important for school counselors and educational planners that will better improve the standard of school curriculum for preventive intervention were made.

Keywords:- Social Activities, Social Adjustment and Students with Deafness.

I. INTRODUCTION

The human body is controlled and protected by the sense organ. These organs are very essential for man's interaction with his environment, the loss or reduction in the abilities of these organs affects the existence of man in his environment. Hearing is the ability to perceive and interpret sounds by detecting vibration through the ear. Deafness is the inability to perceive or identify sounds clearly due to auditory problems. According to Smith (2014), deafness is impairment whether permanent or fluctuating that adversely affects adult's social and educational performance. According to Abang (2005), deafness is a sensory disorder that affects the auditory system of the victim, it is a condition that prevents or limits the perception and interpretation of acoustic signals by the victim.

Okeke (2001) explained that deafness is a disability that affects the total personality no matter the period of onset. When it affects the total personality, it means that it affects the wellbeing of the person which include his social,

physical, psychological and mental state. Hearing difficulty, however, is a disability whose effects are so pervasive that they give rise to the disorganization of the whole personality of the affected. Although mainstream may be beneficial, the social experiences offered within the mainstreamed classroom may not fully facilitate the social development of children with deafness. In a review of the social attainments of children with deafness in general education setting, Feldman-Farb, and Matjasko (2012) found that spending more time integrated into regular education classroom was not related to social acceptance for children with deafness.

Similarly, when children with deafness were placed in inclusive education settings, they tended to have fewer reciprocal relationships than their typical developing peers (Wiener and Tardif, 2004). However, Hermans and Carolein (2016) stated that participating in a dance class which is also a creative drama activity enhances social skills development social relations.

Every social relationship is important experiences that contribute to the development of children's additive social skills. Children's earliest social encounters begin in infancy and continue to increase in complexity as their language develops (Hetherington, Parke, Gauvain, and Locke 2006). By the age of 4, typically developing children can engage in cooperative play with their fellow peers.

Initially, children gain an understanding of how to engage socially by observing the social skills continue as children participate in different interactions that reinforces positive social behaviour (Zarbatany, Haartman and Rankin, 2007). Children also become aware of their undesirable social behaviours when they are given corrective feedback from other children. Social adjustment to other people is general and to the group with which they are identified is particular. P. Priya Packiaselvi and Ms. Makathi 2017, defined social adjustment as the variation of an individual to the social environment, a substantial sign of psychology health a subject fascinating the consideration of many psychologist.

Social growth is the most substantial feature of one's growth and it is assimilated through the relationship with other particularly with the parents, peers and the educators and it is the measuring benchmark of social growth related to the person's adjustment with him or herself and other. When children fail to acquire and enact effective social skills with other children, they are viewed as socially

incompetent by their peers and they are at risk for social isolation (Lamb and Roopnarine, 2009). This isolation further restricts opportunities to practice important skills that can enhance social development in social activities like sport activity, creative drama activity, competition and participating in play.

In general, individuals' social growth will be developed through group social activities including team sports. Exercise by communicating, modeling, reinforcing feedback, social and communication skills, preparation and motivation, emotional development, enhancing adaptability and self-esteem effect the reinforcement of social development of the hearing impaired. Without involvement in social activities, children with deafness are potentially at risk for negative peer experiences like bullying and rejection. Therefore, despite being in the physical proximity of their typically developing classmates, children, with deafness may continue to be socially excluded (Wiener and Tardif, 2004). Persons with deafness constantly makes efforts to adjustment to their surroundings because a wholesome adjustment is essential for leading a happy life and gaining satisfaction.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Socialization and social skills acquisition starts from birth and is influenced by several factors including the participating in sporting activities and other extra-curricular activities. Children with deafness face many challenges as they adjust to the new environment, academic schedules and social challenges (Woosley 2003). Over the year, studies have shown that children with deafness often isolate themselves from partaking in social activities within and outside the school environment, due to inability to communicate with age peers.

Therefore there is a need to find out if involvement of children with deafness in social activities could influences their social adjustment, if gender could ascertain their participation in social activities or adjustment socially. It is based on this that researcher wants to carry out a study to find out whether there will be differences in social adjustment of students with learning impairment in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria who participate in social activities and those who do not take part in social activities.

A. Purpose

The purpose of the study is to ascertain the influence of social activities on social adjustment of students with deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria. Specifically sorts to;

- Ascertain the influence of participation in games (sport activity) on social adjustment of learns with deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria).
- Ascertain the influence of participation in creative drama activity on social adjustments of learns with deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria.

- Ascertain the influence of gender on social adjustment of students with deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria.
- Ascertain the influence of participation in play competition on social adjustment of learns with deafness in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria.

B. Null hypotheses

- There is no substantial influence of games (sport) on the social adjustment of students with deafness.
- There is no substantial influence of creative drama activity on the social adjustment of students with deafness.
- There is no substantial influence of gender on the social adjustment of students with deafness.
- There is no substantial influence of participation in play competition on the social adjustment of students with deafness.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

Descriptive survey research design was adopted.

B. Area of Study

The study was conducted in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria, specifically at: St. Louis School for Inclusive Education Ikot Ekpene which is established and run by the Daughters of Charity of the Catholic Church and Ministry of Education, Special Education School for Persons with Special Needs, Mbiabong Uyo which is established and run by the Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria Government.

C. Population of the Study

The study population included all the persons with deafness in senior secondary school from SSS1 to SSS3 in the two selected Special Education Schools in Special Education Schools in Uyo Nigeria.

D. Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample of 100 students with deafness was selected through purposive sampling technique from the two special schools was used for the study, 50 students from each school. The students were randomly selected from SSS1 – SSS3 from both schools, 25 girls and 25 boys per school.

E. Instrumentation

Influence of social activities on social adjustment of students with deafness questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of 12 items drawn from the variables of the study. The questionnaire has section A and B section A covers personal characteristics of respondents, section B consist of 12 questions drawn from the variables which the respondents have to tick base on the most appropriate of their knowledge from the opinion provided.

IV. RESULTS

A. Hypothesis One

There is no substantial influence of participation in games (sport) on the social adjustment of students with deafness.

Table 1: z- test on influence of participation in games (sport) on the social adjustment of students with deafness

Subjects	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Agreed	73	3.18	0.65	98	6.123	1.960	Reject H0 ₁
Disagreed	27	2.16	0.77				

Table 1 above presents the z-test analysis of influence of participation in games (sport) on the social adjustment of students with deafness. Table 1 indicated that the calculated z -value is 6.123 at 98 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated z-value of 6.123 is greater than the critical table value of 1.960, this hypothesis is rejected. There is therefore a substantial influence of

participation in games (sport) on the social adjustment of students with deafness

B. Null hypotheses Two

There is no substantial influence of participation in creative drama activity on the social adjustment of students with deafness.

Table 2: z – test on influence of participation in creative drama activity on the social adjustment of students with deafness

Subjects	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Agreed	75	3.21	0.64	98	5.657	1.960	Reject H0 ₂
Disagreed	25	2.13	0.88				

Table 2 above presents the z-test analysis of influence of participation in creative drama activity on the social adjustment of students with deafness. Table 2 show that the calculated z -value is 5.657 at 98 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated z-value of 5.657 is greater than the critical table value of 1.960, this hypothesis is rejected. There is therefore a substantial

influence of participation in creative drama activity on the social adjustment of students with deafness

C. Null hypotheses Three

There is no substantial influence of participation in play competition on the social adjustment of students with deafness.

Table 3: z- test on influence of participation in play competition on the social adjustment of students with deafness

Subjects	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Agreed	80	3.31	0.61	98	5.172	1.960	Reject H0 ₃
Disagreed	20	2.20	0.91				

Table 3 above presents the z-test analysis of influence of participation in play competition on the social adjustment of students with deafness. Table 3 indicated that the calculated z -value is 5.172 at 98 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated z-value of 5.172 is greater than the critical table value of 1.960, this hypothesis is rejected. There is therefore a substantial

influence of participation in play competition on the social adjustment of students with deafness.

D. Null hypotheses Four

There is no substantial influence of gender on the social adjustment of students with deafness.

Table 4: z- test on the influence of gender on the social adjustment of students with deafness

Variable	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Decision
Social Adjustment	Male	42	35.93	2.66	98	1.510	1.960	Accept H0 ₄
	Female	58	35.14	2.47				

Table 4 above presents the z-test analysis of the influence of gender on social adjustment of students with deafness. Table 4 indicated that the calculated z -value is 1.510 at 98 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated z -value of 1.510 is less than the critical table value of 1.960, this hypothesis is retained. There is therefore no substantial influence of gender on social adjustment of students with deafness.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

- There is a substantial influence of participation in games (sport) on the social adjustment of students with deafness.
- There is a substantial influence of participation in creative drama activity on the social adjustment of students with deafness.

- There is a substantial influence of participation in play competition on the social adjustment of students with deafness.
- There is no substantial influence of gender on social adjustment of students with deafness.

VI. CONCLUSION

Social activities are those programs which gear towards the development of sense of belongingness, self competence and foster mutual co-operation. Therefore through involvement in social activities, students with deafness will be able to build harmony with oneself, others or the environment, as such maintain or create and adapt a state of positive equilibrium thereby facilitating or improving social interactions between people from different groups.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

On account of the findings of the research the following recommendations are hereby made,

- Social activities should be made a part of both the plus and unique curriculum content for persons with deafness irrespective of their gender.
- School counselors should provide counseling activities for students with deafness on extracurricular activities and its vital role in social skills development.
- Annual competitions such be organized in order to discover and nurture new potentials and talents for students with deafness.
- Educational institutions, professional bodies or associations in special education, non-governmental organizations and government should organize enlighten campaign and sensitize workshop on the importance of participation in social activities.

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